

Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory

To Cite:

Hussain, M. H. Determinants of Fuel Imports in Pakistan: The Role of Fossil Fuel Consumption, Renewable Energy and Economic Growth. *Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory*, Vol. 3, Issue 1, pp. 192-209.

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

*Corresponding author

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

Peer-Review History

Received: 18th May 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 19/May/2024 to 18/June/2024

Accepted: 19th June 2024

Published: 21st June 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory

pISSNxxxx-xxxx; eISSNxxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/archives-of-the-social-sciences-a-journal-of-collaborative-memory>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

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Determinants of Fuel Imports in Pakistan: The Role of Fossil Fuel Consumption, Renewable Energy and Economic Growth

Muhammad Hammad Hussain ^{1*}

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the factors influencing fuel imports in Pakistan, focusing on renewable electricity output, foreign investments, fossil fuel consumption, growth rate, and per capita income, using time-series data from 1990Q1 to 2022Q4. Due to mixed stationarity levels identified by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test, the ARDL model was applied. Short-run results indicate that fuel imports are highly persistent. Renewable energy generation negatively impacts fuel imports, while fossil fuel consumption shows both positive immediate and negative lagged effects. Initially, fuel imports rise with increased renewable energy usage but eventually decline. Growth rate and per capita income also affect fuel imports with negative and positive coefficients, respectively. Long-term analysis reveals that fossil fuel consumption positively impacts fuel imports, whereas renewable electricity generation has a negative effect. Historical fossil fuel consumption reduces current fuel imports. Foreign investments were found to have negligible long-term effects. The study highlights the complex interplay between energy usage, economic factors, and fuel import trends in Pakistan. To reduce fuel imports, policymakers should enhance renewable electricity production and regulate renewable energy use, promote economic growth, and manage per capita income distribution to maintain stable import levels. Additionally, targeted strategies to minimize fossil fuel use and optimize foreign capital effectiveness are recommended.

Keywords: Fuel Imports, Renewable Electricity, Fossil Fuel Consumption; Economic Growth; ARDL estimator; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

For many countries, fuel imports are a crucial lifeline, providing access to vital energy supplies that power daily life and the economy. Imported fuels are essential for supplying the energy needed for industry, home heating, and driving automobiles. However, this dependence on imported fuels has a double-edged effect, shaping the geopolitical, economic, and environmental landscapes by offering both opportunities and challenges. Additionally, the negative environmental effects of using fossil fuels, such as air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, underscore the importance of switching to cleaner, more sustainable energy sources.

High import costs can negatively impact the GDP, exchange rate, inflation, and balance of payments for net oil-importing nations (Gershon and others, 2019). Turkey's primary energy source is natural gas, which is insufficient domestically and thus imported. Russia accounts for 57.9% of these imports, followed by Iran (18.7%) and Azerbaijan (8.6%) (Berk, 2015). Energy is a crucial component of any newly developed economy and is especially important for Pakistan's social and economic development. Over the past decade, Pakistan's energy demand—driven by transportation, industry, and agriculture—has increased rapidly, primarily for imported oil. To meet its economic needs, Pakistan imported 10.68 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) of crude oil from the Middle East (Lin and Raza, 2021). Fossil fuels, including gas, coal, and crude oil, are vital to the world economy. They are the primary sources of electricity for various industrial and residential uses (Shafiee&Topal, 2008). In 2019, fossil fuels accounted for 80% of both domestic energy production and consumption in the United States (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2019). In the European Union (EU) in 2020, oil and petroleum products made up 34.5% of the gross available energy, followed by natural gas (23.7%) and solid fossil fuels (10.2%). In other words, coal, crude oil, and natural gas accounted for 68.4% of the energy produced in the EU (Savage, 2023). The Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis (IEP) projects that India's demand for crude oil will be between 350 and 486 million short tonnes in 2031 and 2032. With an estimated domestic production of 35 million tonnes, India's reliance on imported crude oil will range from 90% to 93% in 2031–2032 (Ghosh, 2009). As economic progress continues, energy demand increases rapidly. Projecting the energy balance for a developing nation with insufficient local energy resources highlights the need to import more fuel, raising concerns about significant pressures on the balance of payments. A notable illustration of the relationship between energy demand and development is the economy of Thailand. Thailand's energy requirements and oil imports have increased significantly (Adam, 2000). Similarly, the energy needs in the North African nations of Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Egypt have grown rapidly in the past and continue to do so. As a result, their political leaders must now consider ways to increase or diversify their countries' generation capacities in response to this change (Führer &Supersberger, 2011). In their effort to transition to a more sustainable energy future, African nations are utilizing a variety of natural resources, making notable advancements in renewable energy markets, and implementing supportive legislation. The global push for clean energy, the need to mitigate climate change, and the importance of renewable energy in achieving sustainable development goals and reducing greenhouse gas emissions all influence the renewable energy markets in Algeria, Angola, Egypt, Ethiopia, South Africa, and Nigeria (IRENA, n.d.; Tambari, 2024). In today's competitive global environment, rapid economic growth has become the cornerstone of an affluent lifestyle everywhere. Regrettably, the current economic expansion is causing harm to the environment and natural ecosystems. Natural resources are scarce and concentrated in a limited number of nations, leading to the dependence of many countries on energy imports. Furthermore, energy imports are a major cause of environmental degradation. To preserve the environment, renewable energy sources are seen as alternatives to non-renewable resources (Malik & Yadav, 2024). Energy usage is a metric commonly used to assess a nation's standard of living. Due to advancements in technology and industry, Pakistan's energy demand has been rising faster than the country's overall supply of primary energy. Only one-sixth of the nation's oil needs are met by domestic sources, while one-third are met by imports [4]. In 2010–11, Pakistan imported petroleum products worth \$10.46 billion and 6.9 million tonnes of crude oil [5]. Reducing Pakistan's heavy dependence on energy imports and the associated expenditure could benefit the economy in three ways: lowering the overall cost of imported fuel, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and making the country's own renewable energy resources more affordable, thereby improving energy security (Anwar, 2016).

Numerous empirical studies have examined the effects of oil price shocks on economic components for oil-importing industrialized economies such as the United States, the European Union, and Japan. Studies by Kurihara (2015) and Akira (2012) indicate that an increase in oil prices can lead to economic growth. The manufacturing sector's share of GDP also suggests that larger shares correspond to higher imports of coal and oil. Additionally, energy use in the transportation sector positively impacts imports of natural gas and oil. The analysis's findings suggest that importing less coal and natural gas, while utilizing renewable energy, can improve energy security. In the context of climate change, nations are also importing less coal and oil while still achieving economic development, but increasing their imports of natural gas due to its role as a transition fuel.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is organized into three sections. The first section explores the relationship between electricity generation, foreign direct investment (FDI), and fuel imports. The second section delves into the connection between fossil fuel consumption, GDP, and fuel imports. The third section investigates the relationship between renewable energy consumption, per capita income, and fuel imports. Khaliq et al. (2024) examined data from 1993 to 2020 to assess the impact of energy commerce, electricity generation and consumption, and the use of ICT. Their findings reveal a long-term trend of increased emissions linked to electricity consumption. Both short- and long-term environmental impacts arise from shocks in fossil fuel-based power production. Negative shocks in renewable and alternative electricity generation lead to ecological degradation due to increased imports of coal, crude oil, metallurgical coke, and ICT. The study suggests that leveraging natural resource rent and trade capabilities could foster an eco-friendlier future for the nation. Zhang et al. (2024) explored the relationship between renewable resources and electricity production, highlighting the importance of affordable energy production as a long-term solution to Pakistan's energy crisis, using data from 1998 to 2018. The results indicate a positive long-term relationship between renewable electricity production, its cost, and environmental quality improvement. The study recommends that Pakistan should (i) prioritize renewable resource development for future energy security, (ii) reduce costs to alleviate consumer burden, (iii) enhance environmental quality, and (iv) integrate renewable energy resources into the national energy policy. Tariq et al. (2023) investigated the long- and short-term relationships between economic globalization, foreign direct investment (FDI), growth, and renewable electricity use in China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) countries, using data from 2000 to 2020. The findings reveal a short-term negative link but a long-term positive relationship between FDI and renewable electricity use. Moreover, there is a

long-term positive correlation and a short-term negative correlation between economic growth and the use of renewable electricity. According to this study, the governments of the BRI nations should promote globalization by developing the knowledge and technology surrounding the use of renewable electricity sources everywhere. Abdouli&Hammami (2020) explored the links between economic growth, foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows, environmental quality, and financial development in Middle Eastern countries using data from 1980 to 2014. The results indicate a bidirectional causal relationship between CO2 emissions and economic growth, FDI inflows and CO2 emissions, and FDI inflows, economic growth, and financial development. The study concludes that Middle Eastern nations must implement robust financial, foreign, and economic policies to foster economic expansion, protect the environment, attract significant FDI inflows, and advance financial development. Goestjahjanti&Novitasari (2023) investigated the impact of non-oil and gas exports on Indonesia's FDI growth, influenced by fluctuations in credit interest rates and fuel prices. The findings show that higher loan interest rates significantly and partially reduce FDI, while fuel prices significantly and positively impact FDI in Indonesia. The study assists Indonesian policymakers in identifying non-oil export sources of FDI, specifically highlighting the roles of fuel prices and credit interest. Nhuong et al. (2024) examined the effects of FDI on Vietnam's sustainable energy transition between 1988 and 2020. The research reveals that in the short term, a 1% increase in FDI is associated with a slight 0.015% decline in the quality of energy transformation, indicating initial negative environmental effects. Long-term, however, a noteworthy improvement of 0.042% in the quality of energy transformation implies that initiatives led by FDI have a favorable impact on sustainable energy practices. Additionally, the Green Economic Growth Index shows a significant positive correlation over both the short and long terms (0.397% and 0.184%, respectively). Vietnam is urged to enact laws that promote the digitization of green projects, establish green funding sources, and offer incentives to environmentally conscious investors. Maarof et al. (2023) assessed how South Africa's use of renewable energy has been impacted by oil prices, fiscal policy, and foreign direct investment (FDI) between 1979 and 2019. The study finds that tax income and economic expansion contribute positively to South Africa's use of renewable energy. However, rising oil prices have a detrimental effect on renewable energy sources in both the short and long terms. Furthermore, the data indicate no significant increase in renewable energy usage with FDI. The results also reveal a one-way causal relationship between renewable energy usage and economic growth. Based on these findings, a policy framework has been proposed to help South Africa achieve sustainable development goals. Appiah-Otoo et al. (2023) analyzed how FDI affects the relationship between renewable energy use and economic growth for a panel of 15 West African countries from 1990 to 2021. The study finds that the use of renewable energy impedes economic growth in West Africa. However, foreign investment promotes economic expansion. The results also show a significant correlation between foreign investment, renewable energy consumption, and economic growth. Consequently, foreign investment increases the consumption of renewable energy, which benefits West Africa's economic expansion.

Dalei & Gupta (2024) aimed to identify the primary causes of climate change, focusing on energy consumption and territorial emissions from fossil fuels. Using data from 1990 to 2018, the study found that GDP per capita and its square in the BRICS countries had an inverted U-shaped relationship with fossil fuel energy consumption. To promote investment in clean and green energy technologies, the study recommends the more vigorous application of climate legislation. Raza et al. (2023) sought to determine the long- and short-term interrelationships among six key variables using time-series yearly data from 1980 to 2020. The study examined the effects of energy consumption, GDP, and urbanization on environmental degradation, specifically CO2 emissions. The findings conclude that: (i) GDP and overall energy consumption have a unidirectional causal relationship with CO2 emissions over both long and short terms; (ii) there is also a short-term causal relationship between energy consumption, the economy, urbanization, and CO2 emissions; (iii) urbanization has a short-term negative impact due to industrialization; and (iv) Bangladesh should implement strict measures to control rising CO2 emissions. Sadat et al. (2024) examined the dynamic effects of various factors on Pakistan's environmental degradation from 1990 to 2020. Key findings include that financial development and GDP per capita negatively impact environmental degradation, indicating improvement in environmental quality with higher financial development and income levels. Renewable energy consumption also negatively impacts environmental degradation, while technological progress positively influences it. The study recommends promoting renewable energy adoption, fostering green innovation, implementing sustainable urban planning techniques, and supporting sustainable economic development. It emphasizes eco-friendly investments by the financial sector. Ramaharo et al. (2024) explored the impact of energy demand on Madagascar's GDP growth from Q1 2007 to Q4 2022. The study found that while energy imports and global pricing negatively impact economic growth in the long term, electricity and petroleum usage have significant positive effects. In the short term, unidirectional causal relationships exist between global prices, energy imports, power consumption, and economic growth. These findings provide policymakers with valuable insights for creating energy policies that support both economic expansion and energy security. Abbasi et al. (2023) investigated the relationships between GDP growth, energy consumption, CO2 emissions, and crude prices in BRICS countries from 1990 to 2022. The study identified a unidirectional causal relationship between fossil fuel consumption and short-term production. Long-term unidirectional relationships were found between fossil fuel consumption, production, and oil prices. The research suggests implementing ecologically conscious strategies such as using biomass, hydropower, and biodiesel to support sustainable development. Additionally, stable global oil prices are deemed necessary for the continued economic growth of BRICS countries, especially for those that are net importers of oil. Zhu et al. (2024) analyzed the impact of energy imports on green innovation in the context of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, using data from 1999 to 2022. The report indicates that increased energy costs negatively affect the development of green innovation in EU countries. The conflict exacerbates the impact, particularly for countries with a high dependency on natural gas (10% to 90%). Natural gas imports indirectly promote green innovation through the energy transition mechanism, while oil imports hinder it by increasing carbon emissions. EU countries relying more than 50% on Russian oil experience more significant negative effects on green innovation development. Lund et al. (2024) examined the factors influencing natural gas (NG) consumption. The study identified population, non-clean energy structure, energy intensity, and per capita GDP as the most impactful elements on NG consumption. The high

Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory, 3(1), 192-209 (2024)

development scenario predicts NG consumption of 42.107 MTOE, double that of the baseline scenario. These findings highlight the critical factors affecting fossil energy structure and natural gas (NG) consumption, providing a basis for future energy policy development. The consumption is expected to rise by 1.5 billion cubic feet per day, while domestic natural gas production is projected to decrease from 4 to 2 billion cubic feet per day. Consequently, an optimized strategy is required to address this growing supply-demand imbalance.

Meng et al. (2023) investigated the effects of natural resource rents and energy imports on sustainable development across 127 countries from 1990 to 2019. The findings indicate that energy imports have a detrimental impact on sustainable development in both the long and short terms. Conversely, the use of domestic natural resource rents has a marginally positive impact on sustainable development. The study also found that globalization and population expansion positively contribute to sustainable development, while corruption has a negative effect. The policy framework should therefore reorient the import of energy and the use of natural resource rents while calibrating the effects of globalization, corruption, and population growth to support sustainable development goals. Yadav & Mahalik (2024) examined the effect of renewable energy usage on energy imports in 16 emerging market economies from 1996 to 2019. The study found that the development of renewable energy only slightly reduces energy imports. It also highlighted that the true effective exchange rate influences energy imports and that globalization can somewhat reduce reliance on energy imports. Additionally, the findings confirm that rising economic growth significantly drives the increased need for energy imports. Tokpah et al. (2024) aimed to investigate the environmental Kuznets curve and the correlations between per capita GDP, fossil fuel consumption, carbon dioxide emissions, oil prices, and foreign direct investment in advanced oil-importing and oil-exporting nations from 1970 to 2020. The study found that fossil fuel use and foreign direct investment reduce CO₂ emissions over time. A key distinction is that in oil-exporting nations, oil prices positively impact CO₂ emissions, while in oil-importing nations, they negatively impact environmental degradation. The report recommends increased investment in renewable energy infrastructure by supporting large-scale projects, boosting research and development, and offering tax breaks and subsidies to renewable energy enterprises. Tambari et al. (2024) investigated the differences between oil-importing and oil-exporting African nations, as well as the symmetric and asymmetric correlations between oil prices and renewable energy investment (REI) in six African countries. The study found that oil prices significantly affect REI in all countries, but the effects vary. For Egypt and Nigeria, symmetric relationships indicate a long-term impact of oil prices on REI, while Algeria shows strong short- and long-term effects. In asymmetric relationships, a long-term increase in oil prices has a considerable negative impact on REI for Angola, Ethiopia, and South Africa, whereas a long-term decrease in oil prices positively influences REI. The study emphasized the necessity of smart policies to encourage the use of renewable energy sources and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Sadat et al. (2024) examined how Pakistan's environmental degradation was dynamically affected between 1990 and 2020 by factors such as GDP, financial development, foreign direct investment, population density, renewable energy use, and technological innovation. The study found that financial development and GDP per capita negatively impact environmental degradation, meaning they improve environmental quality. Renewable energy consumption also negatively impacts environmental degradation, while technological progress has a positive influence. The study recommends promoting renewable energy adoption, fostering green innovation, implementing sustainable urban planning techniques, and supporting sustainable economic development, with a stronger emphasis on eco-friendly investments by the financial sector. Azam et al. (2021) aimed to determine the impact of natural gas, renewable energy, and nuclear energy consumption on economic development and CO₂ emissions in the ten highest CO₂-emitting nations from 1990 to 2014. The results from long-term elasticity and causality tests indicated that natural gas does not contribute to economic growth and CO₂ reduction, unlike nuclear and renewable energy. The study concludes that while natural gas is not beneficial, the development and enhancement of nuclear and renewable energy are essential for preventing climate change and promoting economic prosperity. Dada & Al-Faryan (2024) examined the impact of per capita income (PCI), renewable energy, trade, natural resources, and urbanization on Saudi Arabia's material footprint using data from 1990 to 2019. The findings suggest that PCI, trade, and urbanization significantly increase Saudi Arabia's material footprint, contributing to its ecological impact. In contrast, renewable energy consumption and natural resource rents decrease the material footprint in both short and long terms. Pan & Zaidi (2024) explored how natural resource income and energy imports affect environmental degradation in Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) nations from 1990 to 2020. The research indicates that importing energy from countries focusing on renewable sources can reduce fossil fuel use, contributing to a cleaner environment by lowering the overall carbon footprint. The study recommends that BRICS countries implement policies prioritizing carbon pricing, sustainable resource management, strict regulation, and investment in research and development to mitigate the environmental impact of energy imports, particularly related to natural resource income and natural gas production profitability. Kukharets et al. (2023) analyzed the relationship between renewable energy sources, per capita GDP, and energy import dependency in 27 EU nations from 2011 to 2021. The study concludes that economic development can proceed without increasing energy import dependency if at least 32% of a country's energy comes from renewable sources. As the share of renewable energy increases, a country's reliance on energy imports may even decline. A high level of renewable energy use can boost per capita GDP without significantly increasing energy import dependency. Elevating the proportion of renewable energy sources to above 40% of the EU's overall energy consumption is expected to enhance energy security and independence.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Table 1 shows the list of variables and its measurement.

Table 1: List of Variables

Dependent Variable			
Variables	Symbols	unit	Theoretical expectations
Fuel Imports	FLIMP	% of total	N/A
Independent Variables			
Energy Production From Renewable Resources	EPFR	% of total	-
Foreign Direct Investment	FDI	% of GDP	+/-
Fossil Fuel Energy consumption	FFC	% of total	+
Economic Growth Rate	GDP	Annual %	+/-
Renewable Energy Consumption	REC	% of total	-
Per Capita Income	PCI	Annual %	+

Source: World Bank (2023).

This table provides a clear overview of the variables, their symbols, units, and the theoretical expectations regarding their effects on fuel imports. A time series is considered stationary when its statistical characteristics remain stable over time, meaning that its mean, variance, and autocorrelation structure do not change as a function of time. In a stationary time series, the absence of trends and seasonality implies that the statistical attributes of the data points are uniform and independent of the observation time. Consequently, the relationships and patterns in the data are dependable and can be effectively utilized for accurate forecasting. In a non-stationary time series, the statistical properties vary over time, and the data often exhibit trends and seasonality. These changing statistical characteristics can complicate drawing reliable conclusions or making accurate forecasts. Since the statistical properties of the data are not consistent, any models or analyses based on a non-stationary time series may yield unreliable results.

A Unit Root Test is a statistical technique used in econometrics to assess whether a time series dataset is non-stationary and has a unit root. The presence of a unit root implies that the variable is influenced by random shocks and does not revert to a long-term mean, indicating a lack of long-term trend or stability. These tests are essential in econometrics for analyzing economic data and ensuring that the data is appropriately modeled. Common unit root tests include the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a powerful statistical method used to detect a unit root in a time series, thereby determining if the series is non-stationary. It enhances the original Dickey-Fuller test by incorporating lagged differences of the dependent variable, which helps to account for higher-order autocorrelation. Additionally, the ADF test can optionally include a trend and intercept, allowing it to capture more complex dynamics within the data. By addressing these complexities, the ADF test provides a more robust and reliable assessment of whether a time series is non-stationary.

To test for a unit root in the specified variables with an intercept but no trend, the following will be the form of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) equation:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \sum \delta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \tag{1}$$

Where:

- Δ denotes the difference operator.
- Y_t is the variable of interest.
- α is the intercept.
- γ is the coefficient that we want to test for the unit root.
- δ_i are the coefficients for the lagged differences.
- ϵ_t is the error term.

Equation (1) is further transformed into the studied variables, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta FLIMP &= \alpha + \gamma FLIMP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta FLIMP_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \\ \Delta EPFR &= \alpha + \gamma EPFR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta EPFR_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \\ \Delta FDI &= \alpha + \gamma FDI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \\ \Delta FFC &= \alpha + \gamma FFC_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta FFC_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \\ \Delta GDP &= \alpha + \gamma GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta REC = \alpha + \gamma REC_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta REC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta PCI = \alpha + \gamma PCI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta PCI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Cointegration is a statistical characteristic where a set of time series variables, though individually non-stationary, maintain a stable, long-term relationship. This occurs when a linear combination of these non-stationary variables results in a stationary series. The concept is important in econometrics and finance because it indicates that the variables share a common stochastic trend and tend to revert to equilibrium over time. Testing for cointegration is essential for modeling economic relationships where variables are interconnected in the long term. The Johansen cointegration test is an econometric method used to identify whether multiple non-stationary time series variables share a long-term equilibrium relationship. Unlike the Engle-Granger test, it can manage multiple time series at once, making it especially useful for analyzing complex systems where variables are expected to move in tandem over time. Johansen's test includes two likelihood ratio tests:

1. **Trace Test:** Tests for the number of cointegration relationships.
 2. **Maximum Eigenvalue Test:** Tests for the addition of one more cointegration relationship beyond the hypothesized number.
- These tests analyze the eigenvalues of the matrix to determine the count of cointegrating relationships, with the hypothesis that these relationships imply the series return to equilibrium after disturbances.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is a powerful statistical tool used in econometrics to analyze the dynamic relationships between variables over time. It allows for the examination of both short-term and long-term effects, making it especially useful for understanding complex interactions in economic data. By incorporating both lagged variables and distributed lags, the ARDL model captures the intricate interplay between variables, providing insights into short-term adjustments and long-term equilibria. Known for its versatility and empirical robustness, the ARDL model is a cornerstone in econometric analysis, enabling researchers to uncover underlying patterns shaping economic phenomena across various domains. Error Correction Models (ECM) are designed to analyze short-run dynamics and the speed at which variables adjust towards long-run equilibrium. ECM focuses on the relationship between current changes in variables and their deviations from the long-run equilibrium, highlighting the adjustments needed to return to the equilibrium level.

$$\Delta FLIMP_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \alpha_1 \Delta FLIMP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1-1} \alpha_2 \Delta EPFR_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q2-1} \alpha_3 \Delta FDI_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q3-1} \alpha_4 \Delta FFC_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^{q4-1} \alpha_5 \Delta GDP_{t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^{q5-1} \alpha_6 \Delta REC_{t-n} + \sum_{o=0}^{q6-1} \alpha_2 \Delta PCI_{t-o} + \gamma EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

(2)

The F Bound test is used to determine whether a long-run relationship exists between variables and to identify the appropriate lag length for the variables in an ARDL model. It helps establish the order of integration of the variables and whether cointegration is present. In the next step, once cointegration is estimated, the conditional ARDL (p, q1, q2, q3) long run model derives from following equation:

$$\Delta FLIMP_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta FLIMP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \alpha_2 \Delta EPFR_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q2} \alpha_3 \Delta FDI_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q3} \alpha_4 \Delta FFC_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^{q4} \alpha_5 \Delta GDP_{t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^{q5} \alpha_6 \Delta REC_{t-n} + \sum_{o=0}^{q6} \alpha_2 \Delta PCI_{t-o} + \varepsilon_t$$

(3)

Robust least squares is a regression analysis method that reduces the influence of outliers, providing more reliable parameter estimates when data contain anomalies. This approach modifies the traditional least squares criterion, which minimizes the sum of squared residuals, by applying weighting schemes or alternative norms to lessen the impact of large residuals. The Granger causality test is used in time series analysis to determine if one time series can forecast another. It is based on the premise that if a series X Granger-causes a series Y , then past values of X should contain information that helps predict Y beyond the information contained in past values of Y alone. The equation for this test will be:

$$FLIMP_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \alpha_2 EPFR_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q2} \alpha_3 FDI_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q3} \alpha_4 FFC_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^{q4} \alpha_5 GDP_{t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^{q5} \alpha_6 REC_{t-n} + \sum_{o=0}^{q6} \alpha_2 PCI_{t-o} + \varepsilon_t$$

(4)

Granger causality is tested by checking the significance of the coefficients on lagged values of dependent variable. If these coefficients are statistically significant, we conclude that dependent Granger-causes independent variable. This test assumes stationarity in the data and does not imply true causality, but rather predictive ability. Impulse Response Function (IRF) is an essential concept in time series analysis that describes how a dynamic system reacts over time to external shocks. The IRF measures the impact of a one-time shock to one of the variables in a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model on the current and future values of the endogenous variables within the model. The IRF is determined by calculating the derivative of the future values of X_t with respect to the current shock. This calculation provides insights into the "paths" that these variables take following the shock. Essentially, the IRF

tracks the effect of a unit shock in one variable through the entire system, aiding in the understanding of the dynamics and stability of economic models or financial systems. variance Decomposition Analysis is a technique in time series analysis used to quantify the contribution of each variable's own shocks and the shocks to other variables in a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to the forecast error variance of each variable. This method aids in understanding the dynamics and interrelationships among the variables within a multivariate system. In Variance Decomposition, the proportion of the error variance in forecasting X_t that results from shocks to each variable in the system is computed for several time horizons. The analysis provides insights into the relative importance of each shock to the variables in the system over different periods, illustrating how much each variable's future values are influenced by its own shocks versus shocks to other variables. This analysis is particularly useful in macroeconomics and finance for assessing the impact of economic policies or market events on economic variables.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics and correlation matrix for the variables FLIMP, EPFR, FDI, FFC, GDP, REC, and PCI, including key summary measures such as mean, median, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation for each variable. For FLIMP, the mean and median values are around 6.24 and 6.11, respectively, with a range from 3.89 to 9.91. EPFR shows a higher mean of 8.32 and a narrower range between 6.47 and 11.24. FDI has a mean of 0.23, indicating lower variability, while FFC has a higher mean of 14.63, suggesting greater dispersion. GDP's mean is 1.03, with a narrower range but a negative minimum value. REC has a mean of 12.28, and PCI has a mean of 0.45, both indicating moderate variability. These statistics provide insights into the distribution and variability of each variable, aiding in understanding their characteristics and potential relationships.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix

	FLIMP	EPFR	FDI	FFC	GDP	REC	PCI
Mean	6.2400	8.3239	0.2343	14.6275	1.0331	12.2803	0.4507
Median	6.1147	7.8575	0.1765	14.9032	1.0501	11.9365	0.3594
Maximum	9.9119	11.2430	0.7655	15.6488	2.0452	14.5727	1.4277
Minimum	3.8893	6.4655	0.0608	13.0484	-0.4716	10.4976	-0.8895
Std. Dev.	1.5614	1.2083	0.1664	0.6310	0.5111	0.9937	0.5361
Correlation Matrix							
FLIMP	1.00						

EPFR	-0.64	1.00					
	0.00	----					
FDI	-0.06	-0.07	1.00				
	0.51	0.45	----				
FFC	0.61	-0.83	0.37	1.00			
	0.00	0.00	0.00	----			
GDP	-0.17	0.13	0.03	-0.06	1.00		
	0.05	0.15	0.75	0.51	----		
REC	-0.52	0.73	-0.19	-0.90	-0.01	1.00	
	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.89	----	
PCI	-0.04	-0.02	0.02	0.15	0.96	-0.26	1.00
	0.68	0.84	0.85	0.09	0.00	0.00	----

Source: Author's estimate.

Fuel imports, the dependent variable, shows a moderate negative correlation with renewable electricity output (-0.64), indicating a potential inverse relationship between renewable electricity output and fuel imports. Conversely, it has a moderate positive correlation with fossil fuel consumption (0.61), suggesting a positive association with foreign direct investment. There is a weak negative correlation between fuel imports and growth rate (-0.17), implying a slight decrease in fuel imports as gross domestic product increases. Fuel imports also exhibits a moderate negative correlation with renewable energy consumption (-0.52), pointing to a potential inverse relationship with renewable energy consumption. However, the correlations between fuel imports and both foreign investment and per capita income are weak and not statistically significant. Overall, these correlations suggest that fuel imports is influenced by foreign portfolio investment, foreign direct investment, gross domestic product, and real exchange rates, with each variable affecting fuel imports in different ways. The ADF unit root test was used for checking the stationarity of the variables in this study. The results of showed that some of the variables are of order I(0) and others of order I(1) (see, Table 3).

Table 3: ADF Test Results

Variable	LEVEL		1ST DIFFERENCE		DECISION
	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	
FLIMP	-2.07978	-3.33207	-3.57653	-3.58539	I(1)
	0.25320	0.06580	0.00760	0.03510	
EPFR	-2.91585	-2.38977	-2.57716	-2.76008	I(0)
	0.04640	0.38300	0.10060	0.21510	
FDI	-2.95786	-3.02137	-3.27258	-3.31549	I(0)
	0.04180	0.13060	0.01830	0.06840	
FFC	-2.84136	-2.09550	-3.10795	-3.66376	I(1)
	0.05550	0.54280	0.02850	0.02870	
GDP	-2.96043	-2.95707	-3.35386	-3.34983	I(0)
	0.04160	0.14880	0.01470	0.06340	
REC	-2.11533	-2.27873	-3.26681	-3.55119	I(1)
	0.23910	0.44190	0.01860	0.03850	
PCI	-2.66765	-2.78944	-3.04111	-3.05037	I(1)
	0.08270	0.20410	0.03400	0.12330	

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 3 presents the unit root test results for the variables FLIMP, EPFR, FDI, FFC, GDP, REC, and PCI, indicating their integration order, whether I(0) or I(1). Under both intercept-only and intercept with trend models, fuel imports, fossil fuel consumption, renewable energy consumption, and per capita income are integrated of order 1 (I(1)), indicating they are non-stationary at levels but become stationary after first differencing. On the other hand, renewable electricity output, foreign investment, and growth rate are integrated of order 0 (I(0)), meaning they are stationary at levels and do not require differencing. These results provide important insights into the stationarity properties of the variables, which are crucial for determining the appropriate specifications in time series modeling and forecasting. The VAR Lag Length Selection Criteria in Table 4 provides information for determining the optimal number of lags in a Vector Autoregressive model.

Table 4: VAR Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0.00	-348.94	NA	0.00	5.48	5.63	5.54
1.00	1040.14	2607.20	0.00	-15.14	-13.91	-14.64
2.00	1270.22	407.0623*	3.89e-17*	-17.92649*	-15.61040*	-16.98538*

Source: Author's estimate.

The rows represent different lag lengths (0, 1, and 2), while the columns display various statistics and criteria for selection. At lag 0, the log likelihood is -348.94, and no likelihood ratio statistic is available. The Final Prediction Error, Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Criterion and Hannan-Quinn Criterion are also reported, with higher values indicating a poorer model fit. At lag 1, the model fit improves significantly, shown by a higher LogL (1040.14) and much lower AIC, SC, and HQ values. The most substantial improvement occurs at lag 2, where the LogL increases to 1270.22. At this lag, the LR statistic, FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ reach their optimal values (indicated by asterisks), suggesting that lag 2 is the best choice for the VAR model according to multiple selection metrics. Table 5 presents the results of cointegration tests conducted under various model specifications to assess the presence and nature of long-term relationships among variables in a dataset. Each row represents a different model configuration, including assumptions about data trends ("None" or "Linear") and the inclusion of intercepts and trends ("No Intercept," "Intercept," "No Trend," and "Trend").

Table 5: Pantula Test Estimates

Data Trend	None	None	Linear	Linear	Quadratic
Test Type	No Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept
	No Trend	No Trend	No Trend	Trend	Trend
Trace	1	2	3	3	3
Max-Eig	1	2	2	0	0

The "Trace" and "Max-Eig" columns report the test statistics for the number of cointegrating relationships, with higher values indicating stronger evidence of cointegration. Specifically, models that include linear trends and intercepts, whether or not they consider trends, show more cointegrating vectors (values of 2 or 3), suggesting stronger evidence of long-term relationships among variables when linear trends and intercepts are included. The Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace) results in Table 6 indicate the presence of two cointegrating equations among the variables in the model at the 0.05 significance level. The trace test rejects the null hypothesis of no cointegration and at most one cointegrating equation, as the trace statistics (165.73 and 117.98) exceed their critical values (134.68 and 103.85) with p-values of 0.00. However, for the hypothesis of at most two cointegrating equations, the trace statistic (76.18) is slightly below the critical value (76.97) with a p-value of 0.06, suggesting no more than two cointegrating relationships. Therefore, the test confirms the presence of two long-term equilibrium relationships among the variables.

Table 6: Johanson Cointegration Results

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.31	165.73	134.68	0.00
At most 1 *	0.28	117.98	103.85	0.00
At most 2	0.21	76.18	76.97	0.06
At most 3	0.15	46.14	54.08	0.21
At most 4	0.09	25.85	35.19	0.35
At most 5	0.07	13.80	20.26	0.30
At most 6	0.03	4.42	9.16	0.35
Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.31	47.75	47.08	0.04
At most 1 *	0.28	41.80	40.96	0.04
At most 2	0.21	30.05	34.81	0.17
At most 3	0.15	20.28	28.59	0.39
At most 4	0.09	12.05	22.30	0.65
At most 5	0.07	9.39	15.89	0.39
At most 6	0.03	4.42	9.16	0.35
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's estimate.

Similarly, the Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue) results suggest the presence of two cointegrating equations among the variables at the 0.05 significance level. The test rejects the null hypothesis of no cointegration and at most one cointegrating equation, as the max-eigen statistics (47.75 and 41.80) exceed their critical values (47.08 and 40.96) with p-values of 0.04. However, for the hypothesis of at most two cointegrating equations, the max-eigen statistic (30.05) is below the critical value (34.81) with a p-value of 0.17, indicating no more than two cointegrating relationships. Thus, this test also confirms the existence of two long-term equilibrium relationships among the variables. The ARDL Error Correction Model (ECM) regression results in Table 7 offer a detailed understanding of the short-term dynamics and long-term equilibrium relationship of fuel imports with other variables. The lagged variable of fuel imports (FLIMP(-1)) has a positive coefficient of 0.68, indicating a remarkable persistence of fuel import levels over time in Pakistan. This implies that historical fluctuations in fuel import levels typically have a significant influence on present import levels. Pakistan's high reliance on imported fuel to cover its energy consumption, combined with its low domestic supply,

might be blamed for this persistence. This dynamic is influenced by changes in the price of oil globally, the rate of economic expansion, and the patterns of energy consumption.

Table 7: ARDL Error Correction Model Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FLIMP(-1))	0.68	0.06	11.03	0.00
D(EPFR)	-0.31	0.14	-2.27	0.03
D(EPFR(-1))	0.19	0.13	1.45	0.15
D(FFC)	2.12	0.45	4.67	0.00
D(FFC(-1))	-1.76	0.46	-3.83	0.00
D(GDP)	-2.74	1.51	-1.81	0.07
D(REC)	3.33	0.44	7.61	0.00
D(REC(-1))	-2.50	0.44	-5.67	0.00
D(PCI)	2.86	1.54	1.86	0.07
CointEq(-1)*	-0.08	0.02	-3.69	0.00
Statistical Results				
R-squared	0.63	Mean dependent var	0.04	
Adjusted R-squared	0.60	S.D. dependent var	0.37	
S.E. of regression	0.23	Akaike info criterion	-0.02	
Sum squared resid	6.43	Schwarz criterion	0.21	
Log likelihood	10.99	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.07	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.24			

Source: Author's estimate.

Conversely, renewable electricity production exerts a negative impact on fuel imports (-0.31), as is pointed by Kukharets et al (2023). A country's economic development can proceed without increasing its reliance on energy imports if its share of energy comes from renewable sources is at least 32%. In fact, a country's reliance on energy imports may even decline as its share of energy from renewable sources increases. A country's energy security and degree of energy independence will rise if its use of renewable energy sources rises to more than 40% of its overall energy resource consumption, as will the case throughout the European Union. The coefficient of -0.31, which represents the negative relationship between renewable power output and fuel imports, indicates that a rise in renewable energy generation in Pakistan is associated with a decrease in fuel imports. This relationship demonstrates how the nation is working to invest in renewable energy sources including hydro, solar, and wind power in order to diversify its energy mix and lessen its reliance on imported fossil fuels. Fuel imports become less necessary as renewable energy capacity increases, improving energy security and lessening the financial burden of fuel import expenditures. This change is in line with Pakistan's strategic objectives to increase economic resilience against volatile global fuel costs, promote sustainability, and lessen environmental effect.

The results showed that fossil fuel consumption and fuel imports were associated positively. Hank et al. (2020). provide support for these findings, they show that energy is needed for all commercial processes, such as force, lighting, heating, and cooling, as well as for technologies used in offices, power plants, and automobiles. Fibres that have a high voltage and quick response are the preferred energy source. The need to purchase fuel reserves from other countries arises from the growing use of fossil fuels. Furthermore in line with Ioannidis, Chalvatzis, Li, Notton, and Stephanides (2019) are these results. They point out that the need for fuel imports rises with the growing usage of fossil fuels like coal, oil, and petroleum. The consumption of fossil fuels has a positive coefficient (2.12), meaning that fuel imports of Pakistan are greatly increased when fossil fuel consumption rises. This close association highlights the nation's significant reliance on imported fossil fuels to meet its energy needs. Fossil fuels including coal, natural gas, and oil are crucial to Pakistan's industrial development, transportation requirements, and electrical production. As a result, any increase in domestic consumption causes larger levels of imports to be required to keep up with demand.

The usage of renewable energy at the moment has a positive impact on fuel imports (3.33), while its lag effect has a negative impact (-2.50). Because of the increased economic activity and probable need for supplemental fossil fuels during the transition phase, the adoption of renewable energy technologies may initially need considerable imports of infrastructure and equipment, thereby increasing fuel import levels. However, the need for fuel imports gradually declines as renewable energy projects go online and begin to replace the use of fossil fuels. The long-term energy independence and sustainability goals are supported by the negative lag effect, which shows that consistent investments in renewables progressively lessen dependency on imported fossil fuels. This trend emphasises the significance of maintaining dedication to the development of renewable energy sources, weighing the long-term advantages of less reliance on fossil fuels against temporary increases in imports.

Short-term fuel imports are negatively impacted by the growth rate (-2.74), indicating that fuel imports initially decline as Pakistan's economy grows. Numerous causes can account for this unexpected outcome. In the near run, economic expansion may

improve energy efficiency and encourage infrastructure and technology investments that lower fuel usage. Fuel imports may be momentarily reduced by, for instance, increased industry energy efficiency, the adoption of better transportation technologies, and a move towards less energy-intensive economic activity. Better fiscal health can also result from increasing economic activity, which enables the government to encourage and subsidise domestic energy generation and lessen need on imports.

The effect of per capita income on fuel imports is positive (2.86), supported by Fedoseeva&Zeidan (2018), (Asymmetric) Income seems to be the most relevant determinant of import demand, indicates that as individuals' income levels rise, the demand for imported fuels increases. Greater consumption of energy-intensive goods and services, such as increasing use of personal vehicles, higher power usage for home appliances, and increased industrial production, is generally associated with higher per capita income. The general demand for fuel rises as people's disposable income increases and they tend to buy more energy-intensive goods and services. Furthermore, urbanisation and greater living standards are two further factors that raise energy use when income levels rise.

The significant negative coefficient of the error correction term (-0.08) indicates that deviations from the long-term equilibrium are corrected, suggesting a stabilizing mechanism in the model. Overall, the model provides valuable insights into the intricate dynamics of fuel imports and its relationship with other economic variables, with robust explanatory power (60-63%) and no significant autocorrelation issues.

The ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test in Table 8 provide insights into the long-term relationship among the variables and the bounds of the model. In the conditional error correction regression, the coefficient for FLIMP(-1) (-0.08) indicates that deviations from equilibrium are corrected by approximately 8% each period, affirming the presence of a long-term equilibrium relationship. Pakistan's long-term reliance on imported fossil fuels to meet its energy needs is highlighted by the positive impact of fossil fuel use on fuel imports (2.12). Hank et al. (2020) provide support for these findings, Improving economic development, industrial growth, and growing energy demands all contribute to rising fossil fuel use, which in turn drives up demand for coal, natural gas, and oil imports. Pakistan must import a significant amount of energy due to its limited native fossil fuel resources not being able to meet its expanding energy needs.

Table 8: ARDL Long Run Form Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-3.93	3.19	-1.23	0.22
FLIMP(-1)*	-0.08	0.03	-3.07	0.00
EPFR(-1)	0.04	0.05	0.82	0.42
FDI**	-0.31	0.23	-1.36	0.18
FFC(-1)	0.28	0.16	1.70	0.09
GDP(-1)	0.26	0.40	0.64	0.52
REC(-1)	0.00	0.10	-0.02	0.99
PCI(-1)	-0.26	0.40	-0.64	0.52
D(FLIMP(-1))	0.68	0.07	9.42	0.00
D(EPFR)	-0.31	0.15	-2.06	0.04
D(EPFR(-1))	0.19	0.14	1.36	0.18
D(FFC)	2.12	0.51	4.20	0.00
D(FFC(-1))	-1.76	0.51	-3.47	0.00
D(GDP)	-2.74	1.67	-1.64	0.10
D(REC)	3.33	0.49	6.75	0.00
D(REC(-1))	-2.50	0.48	-5.22	0.00
D(PCI)	2.86	1.70	1.68	0.10

Source: Author's estimate.

The long-term positive impact of renewable energy consumption in Pakistan on fuel imports (3.33), together with its negative lagged effect (-2.50), is indicative of the country's energy infrastructure development transitional period. Importing technology, apparatus, and related fossil fuels for installation and operational support initially raises fuel imports as Pakistan makes investments in renewable energy. But as renewable energy sources are put into service and begin to provide electricity, they gradually lessen the need for fossil fuels, which lowers the amount of fuel imported. Ultimately, the significant and negative impact of renewable electricity generation on petroleum imports (-0.31) in Pakistan underscores the nation's deliberate transition to sustainable energy sources, which is supported by Kukharets et al (2023) The amount of imported fossil fuels required for power generation decreases as the amount of electricity generated by renewable sources rises. This shift improves energy security and lowers the cost of fuel imports. The fact that the coefficient is negative highlights how well renewable energy policies and investments work to reduce long-term dependency on fuel imports, promoting both environmental sustainability and economic resilience against fluctuations in the price of fuel globally. This outcome encourages the further development of renewable energy initiatives in Pakistan in order to create a more stable and self-

sufficient energy sector. Conversely, $D(\text{FLIMP}(-1))$ (0.68) shows a significant positive coefficient, indicating the persistence of fuel imports changes over time. These findings collectively underscore the robustness of the long-term relationship between the variables in the model. The F-Bounds Test in Table 9 assesses whether a long-run relationship exists among the variables

Table 9: ARDL Bounds Test Estimates

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
		Asymptotic: n=1000		
F-statistic	1.60	0.10	1.99	2.94
K	6.00	0.05	2.27	3.28
		0.03	2.55	3.61
		0.01	2.88	3.99
Actual Sample Size		Finite Sample: n=80		
		0.10	2.09	3.10
		0.05	2.43	3.52
		0.01	3.17	4.49

Source: Author's estimate.

The null hypothesis is "No levels relationship." The test statistic values vary across significance levels and sample sizes. For instance, at a significance level of 0.05 with a finite sample size of 80, the critical F-statistic value is 2.43, suggesting insignificance at this level. However, at a significance level of 0.01, the critical F-statistic value rises to 3.17, indicating significance at a higher level of confidence. These findings suggest that there may indeed be a long-run relationship among the variables, particularly at higher significance levels. This provides important insights into their interdependencies over time. The results from Robust Least Squares estimation method with Huber Type I Standard Errors & Covariance in Table 10 provide robust parameter estimates of the model revealing complex effects of each independent variable on dependent variable.

Table 10: Robust Least Squares Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
EPFR	1.27	0.15	8.30	0.00
FDI	-21.96	0.69	-31.64	0.00
FFC	4.63	0.46	10.13	0.00
GDP	5.55	1.14	4.88	0.00
REC	-0.29	0.25	-1.14	0.25
PCI	-6.36	1.14	-5.58	0.00
C	-67.09	9.13	-7.34	0.00
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.42	Adjusted R-squared		0.39
Scale	1.09	Deviance		1.19
Rn-squared statistic	1579.39	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)		0.00
Non-robust Statistics				
Mean dependent var	6.24	S.D. dependent var		1.56
S.E. of regression	3.04	Sum squared resid		1153.70

Source: Author's estimate.

In particular, the coefficient of renewable electricity production (1.27) is significantly positive which shows that its increase results in a significant rise for fuel imports. In contrast, foreign investment (-21.96) has a significantly negative coefficient indicating its increase will reduce fuel imports. Also, fossil fuel usage (4.63) and growth rate (5.55) show significant positive coefficient suggesting that higher the value of fossil fuel consumption and growth rate greater is the impact on fuel imports. On the other hand, per capita income (-6.36) has a significant negative coefficient, suggesting that its increase negatively affect fuel imports. Overall, these findings offer valuable insights into the complex relationships between the independent variables and fuel imports, highlighting both positive and negative effects on fuel import's dynamics. The Granger causality tests in Table 11 indicate that renewable energy consumption, fossil fuel consumption and renewable electricity generation exhibit potential influence on fuel imports.

Table 11: Granger Causality Test Estimates

Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Prob.
EPFR → FLIMP	2.77395	0.0663
FLIMP → EPFR	0.95658	0.387
FDI → FLIMP	0.53162	0.589
FLIMP → FDI	2.42185	0.0929
FFC → FLIMP	2.70297	0.0709
FLIMP → FFC	0.07092	0.9316
GDP → FLIMP	0.24902	0.78
FLIMP → GDP	1.42137	0.2453
REC → FLIMP	4.00359	0.0206
FLIMP → REC	0.07761	0.9254
PCI → FLIMP	0.42469	0.6549
FLIMP → PCI	0.54489	0.5813

Source: Author's estimate.

Renewable energy consumption, with a p-value of 0.0206, significantly Granger-causes fuel imports. Fossil fuel consumption, with a p-value of 0.0709, and renewable electricity output, with a p-value of 0.0663, also suggest possible Granger causal relationships with fuel imports, implying their influence on fuel imports might be noteworthy. Conversely, the variables foreign investment, growth rate, per capita income, and the reciprocal relationships with fuel imports do not demonstrate statistically significant Granger causality. Figure 1 shows the IRF estimates for ready reference.

Figure 1: IRF Estimates

Source: Author's work.

The impulse response graphs illustrate how fuel imports responds over time to shocks in various variables, with the blue line representing the response and the dotted red lines indicating confidence intervals. For renewable electricity generation, foreign investment and growth rate, the response of fuel imports is relatively stable and does not show significant deviation from zero, indicating minimal impact. The responses to shocks in fossil fuel consumption and per capita income display a slight downward trend but remain within the confidence intervals, suggesting a modest and statistically insignificant effect. In contrast, the response to a shock in renewable energy consumption shows a more pronounced and persistent negative trend, which is outside the confidence intervals, indicating a significant and lasting impact of renewable energy consumption on fuel imports. Overall, these graphs suggest that renewable energy consumption has a notable influence on fuel imports, while other variables exhibit minimal or statistically insignificant impacts. The variance decomposition in Table 12 of fuel imports indicates how much of its forecast error variance is attributed to itself and other economic variables over ten periods. Initially, fuel imports accounts for 100% of its variance in period 1.

Table 12: Variance Decomposition Analysis

Variance Decomposition of FLIMP								
Period	S.E.	FLIMP	EPFR	FDI	FFC	GDP	REC	PCI
1	0.279388	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.502237	99.39038	0.126833	0.139495	0.150564	0.014196	0.164547	0.013985
3	0.690032	97.78619	0.381289	0.548439	0.546494	0.103677	0.622815	0.011093
4	0.843951	95.18376	0.707273	1.234393	1.168804	0.295359	1.395542	0.014873
5	0.96985	91.74479	1.06857	2.140928	1.965872	0.541862	2.458818	0.079156
6	1.073217	87.77036	1.443126	3.169473	2.871754	0.759165	3.744737	0.241386
7	1.157995	83.59685	1.819566	4.21073	3.826573	0.886913	5.158533	0.500833
8	1.226913	79.51345	2.192957	5.167846	4.786545	0.917473	6.598731	0.823
9	1.282066	75.73323	2.560882	5.967735	5.723735	0.884363	7.972723	1.157333
10	1.325299	72.39815	2.920822	6.565406	6.621113	0.832579	9.206544	1.455387

Source: Author's estimate.

As time progresses, the influence of other variables increases. By period 10, fuel import's own contribution to its variance drops to 72.4%, while other factors like renewable electricity generation, foreign investment, fossil fuel consumption, growth rate, renewable energy consumption and per capita income cumulatively account for the remaining 27.6%. Among these, growth rate and foreign investment emerge as significant contributors, explaining 9.2% and 6.6% of the variance, respectively, by the tenth period. This indicates that over time, the fluctuations in fuel imports are increasingly influenced by the broader economic environment and interactions with other economic variables.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study aims to examine the impact of renewable electricity output, foreign investments, fossil fuel consumption, growth rate, renewable energy consumption, and per capita income on fuel imports in Pakistan. Utilizing time-series data from 1990Q1 to 2022Q4, the research employs the ARDL model to explore the co-movements and connections among these variables. In the short run, the results show that fuel imports are highly persistent, with past changes significantly and positively affecting current values. The analysis reveals that renewable electricity generation has a negative impact on fuel imports, suggesting that increases in renewable energy lead to a short-term decrease in fuel imports. This inverse relationship highlights the importance of renewable energy in reducing reliance on fuel imports. Conversely, the consumption of fossil fuels has a complex effect, with current increases boosting fuel imports while past increases have an offsetting negative impact. This indicates a direct immediate impact of fossil fuel consumption on fuel imports, followed by a corrective effect over time. Additionally, renewable energy consumption has a robust positive influence on fuel imports in the short term, but its lagged effect demonstrates a negative impact, suggesting that initial increases in renewable energy consumption are followed by a reduction in fuel imports. The study also finds that growth rate and per capita income contribute to fluctuations in fuel imports. Specifically, the growth rate has a negative impact, while per capita income shows a positive effect, indicating that these economic factors play a significant role in influencing fuel import levels. In the long run, the results demonstrate that fossil fuel consumption continues to have a positive impact on fuel imports, reinforcing the need to manage fossil fuel usage carefully. Similarly, the usage of renewable energy has a positive impact on fuel imports initially, but its long-term effect is negative, emphasizing the potential of renewable energy to reduce fuel imports over an extended period. The persistence of fuel imports over time is further confirmed by the significant positive coefficient for past changes in fuel imports.

Based on these findings, the study provides several policy recommendations. To effectively manage and potentially reduce fuel imports in Pakistan, it is crucial to adopt a structured approach across different time horizons. In the short term, enhancing the efficiency of current fuel use in key sectors such as transportation and industry can immediately decrease the volume of imports. For the medium term, strategies should focus on expanding domestic energy production capabilities by exploring and developing local fossil fuel resources and alternative energy sources like biofuels. Long-term policies should aim at significantly reducing reliance on external fuel sources by investing heavily in renewable energy technologies and infrastructure, creating a robust and sustainable

energy mix. This should be coupled with policy measures that promote energy conservation and efficiency across all sectors of the economy. Together, these steps will help stabilize Pakistan's energy supply, reduce economic vulnerability to external shocks, and support broader economic objectives of growth and sustainability. To leverage the positive impact of renewable electricity generation on reducing fuel imports, Pakistan should further invest in expanding its renewable energy infrastructure. Policies should encourage the development of solar, wind, and hydropower projects by providing tax incentives, subsidies, and favorable financing options. Streamlining regulatory approvals and facilitating public-private partnerships can also attract investment in renewable electricity generation, thereby reducing dependence on fuel imports. In the short term, the government should prioritize developing small-scale renewable projects that utilize local resources, such as solar panels in rural areas, to quickly reduce dependency on fuel imports. In the medium term, policies should focus on establishing incentives for both local and foreign investments in renewable energy sectors, including tax rebates and subsidized loans. Additionally, integrating renewable energy education in academic curricula will cultivate a knowledgeable workforce. In the long term, comprehensive infrastructure upgrades are crucial, alongside the establishment of a legal framework that supports large-scale renewable projects. This approach will not only decrease the country's reliance on imported fuels but also bolster economic growth and environmental sustainability. To benefit from the negative impact of foreign investment on fuel imports, Pakistan should aim to attract more FDI into its energy sector, particularly in renewable and efficient energy projects. This can be achieved by creating a stable and transparent regulatory environment, offering tax incentives, and simplifying investment procedures. Improving infrastructure and ensuring political stability will make Pakistan a more attractive destination for foreign investors, reducing reliance on fuel imports through enhanced local energy production. In the short term, the government should streamline and simplify investment processes to reduce bureaucracy and enhance transparency, making it easier for investors to enter the market. In the medium term, it is crucial to establish public-private partnerships that leverage FDI to build renewable energy infrastructure, supported by stable economic policies and incentives such as tax holidays and guaranteed returns on investment. For the long term, the focus should be on creating a robust legal framework that protects foreign investors while aligning their operations with national energy goals and sustainable development plans. These steps will not only reduce dependency on fossil fuel imports but also promote economic growth through enhanced energy security and job creation in renewable sectors.

Given the complex relationship between fossil fuel consumption and fuel imports, policies should focus on promoting energy efficiency and transitioning to cleaner energy sources. Implementing energy efficiency standards, investing in technologies to reduce fossil fuel consumption, and encouraging alternative energy use are key steps. Gradually phasing out fossil fuel subsidies and reallocating those funds to support renewable energy projects can help manage fossil fuel demand and reduce fuel imports. In the short term, the government should implement stringent regulations on fossil fuel use in industrial operations and promote energy efficiency measures across all sectors to immediately curb consumption. For the medium term, investment in renewable infrastructure, supported by financial incentives such as subsidies and low-interest loans for solar, wind, and hydro projects, will gradually replace the energy mix's dependency on fossil fuels. Long-term strategies should focus on comprehensive national energy policies that mandate a significant share of energy generation from renewables, coupled with the phasing out of fossil fuel subsidies to discourage their use. These steps will help Pakistan reduce its reliance on imported fuels while achieving economic stability and environmental sustainability. The negative impact of GDP growth on fuel imports suggests that sustainable economic growth can reduce reliance on fuel imports. Policies should focus on fostering inclusive and sustainable growth by improving infrastructure, education, and innovation. Investing in less energy-intensive sectors and promoting energy-efficient practices across industries can support economic growth while minimizing fuel imports. Encouraging the development of a diversified economy can also contribute to this goal. In the short term, the government should reallocate portions of the GDP towards rapid deployment of renewable energy projects to immediately start reducing fuel dependency. In the medium term, investing in technology transfer and capacity building within the renewable sector can create jobs and stimulate economic activities, thereby further increasing the GDP. For the long term, policies should aim at integrating renewable energy production into broader economic planning, ensuring that a significant portion of economic growth is sustainably reinvested into expanding renewable energy capabilities. This strategy will not only help curtail fuel imports but also support sustained economic growth by creating a resilient and green energy sector. To harness the positive impact of renewable energy consumption on reducing fuel imports, Pakistan should increase the use of renewable energy. Providing subsidies and financial incentives for residential and industrial adoption of renewable energy technologies can drive this transition. Public awareness campaigns on the benefits of renewable energy, along with supportive policies like net metering and feed-in tariffs, will encourage higher consumption rates, thereby reducing fuel imports. In the short term, policies should encourage immediate investment in renewable energy sectors to kick start economic activities and reduce the immediate load on fossil fuel consumption. For the medium term, the focus should shift towards strengthening the infrastructure and technological base of renewable resources, which can drive sustainable economic growth and create employment opportunities. In the long term, the government should aim to integrate renewable energy fully into the national grid and economic planning, ensuring that a significant portion of economic growth is driven by green energy sectors. This integration will not only help reduce fuel imports but also promote a resilient, sustainable economic structure that can fuel further growth.

Considering that per capita income in Pakistan is relatively low, policies should focus on making energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy solutions affordable and accessible. Introducing subsidies and financial assistance for low-income households to adopt energy-efficient appliances and renewable energy systems can help. Public education campaigns on energy conservation and the economic benefits of reducing fuel consumption will also be effective. Encouraging community-based renewable energy projects and providing support for small-scale renewable energy installations can further mitigate the impact on fuel imports. In the short term, the focus should be on generating labor-intensive jobs in both traditional and renewable energy sectors to quickly absorb a large workforce. For the medium term, emphasis should be placed on vocational training and upskilling programs tailored to the needs of

emerging sectors, including renewable energy and energy efficiency services, to help workers secure better-paying jobs. In the long term, strategies should aim to transition the economic base towards high-value, technology-driven industries by fostering innovation, supporting startups in the energy and technology sectors, and attracting foreign direct investment. This gradual transformation, supported by a stable and supportive policy environment, will increase per capita income, reduce poverty levels, and decrease reliance on energy imports, thereby enhancing economic stability and resilience in Pakistan.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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